

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

DCSTAMP induction by Streptococcus pneumonia.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Streptococcus pneumonia is a leading contributor to infection in the community. We modeled S. pneumonia infection in primary macrophages derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells and used RNA-sequencing to measure total transcription during infection. We describe here for the first time a function for the dendritic cell-specific transmembrane protein, DCSTAMP, encoded by *TM7SF4* in gram-positive S. pneumoniae infection.